

Alternative ways of European participatory organic fruit breeding projects

CTIFL - Organic fruit testing in France

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CTIFL

Created in 1952, CTIFL is the referent organisation for applied research in the French fruit and vegetable sector. Through its studies and innovations, it contributes to the development and the diversification of production and marketing methods for all actors involved in the value chain.

CTIFL conducts programmes covering experimentation and research, driving innovation, monitoring economic and regulatory developments, and ensuring training sessions and dissemination of information to the fruit and vegetable sector. Designated as a competent authority, CTIFL is in charge of the inspection and certification of fruit plant propagation material, strawberry plants excepted.

The institute activities are positioned around 5 themes:

- Searching for alternatives to pesticides
- Maintaining the quality of fruits and vegetables all the way to the consumer
- Reducing the use of fossil energy in greenhouses
- Studying and developing solutions for mechanisation and automation
- Evolution of fruit and vegetable consumption patterns

Activities involving research, validation and dissemination of technical references are conducted at all CTIFL centres and sites including Balandran, Carquefou, Lanxade, Saint-Rémy-de Provence, Rungis, Nancy, La Morinière, La Tapy, and Brindas. Each location has at its disposal experimentation facilities allowing various scales of research, from crop to consumer, such as open field plots, tunnels, glasshouses, orchards, laboratories, climatic chambers, cold storage and ripening rooms, point-of-sale simulation area.

CTIFL has 5 centres, 4 antennas and 1 head quarter

Two case study sites: Balandran and La Morinière

The CTIFL case studies are located in two sites in France: CTIFL Balandran near Nîmes in the South East and CTIFL La Morinière near Tours in the North West. Three species are involved in the project: stone fruits (apricot and peaches) and pip fruits (apple), all three species in organic production.

The case study in Balandran aims to develop and sustain the organic production of stone fruits in the region, by providing technical and scientific references and cultural practices that can be used by producers. The objectives of the project are to evaluate, describe and identify varieties of stone fruits suitable for organic farming and corresponding to the commercial expectations of the sector. Organic varietal evaluation has been carried out on peach varieties since 2015 and apricot varieties since 2016. 17 varieties of apricots and 15 varieties of peach (yellow and white peaches and nectarines) are chosen to be evaluated for organic production.

The identification of new varieties of stone fruits suitable for organic farming is carried out by a survey of the behaviour of varieties among professionals in the organic sector and the evaluation of new varieties in our experimental stations in order to evaluate their agronomic performances and their interest for the different commercial circuits.

A number of traits are measured, related to phenology (e.g. blooming and fruit set), tree development (e.g. vigour and yield), fruit quality (e.g. size, colour, taste), abiotic stresses (e.g. skin cracking) and biotic stresses (e.g. Brown rot/Monilinia on flowers, rust diseases on leaves).

The case study in La Morinière is based on the organic orchard of the centre. This orchard was created in 1999 to answer to the grower's problem. From the outset, producers asked for an assessment of the behaviour of new varieties of apples and pears. For each new cultivar, 10 trees were planted and observed, including diseases and pest sensitivities, annual yield and quality during storage of fruits. There are scab resistant apples and some cultivars tolerant to scab and aphids. There are also varieties without known resistances. In the Loire valley, the most concerning diseases in organic fruit growing are scab and gloeosporium in storage. For pest, the most important issues are codling moth, blossom weevil, aphids and apple sawfly. On pears, problems are blossom weevil and sawfly. Growers are very attentive to yield production and balance of trees. Around 23 new apple varieties in our organic orchard are followed.

InnOBreed collaboration

Since 2022, the CTIFL is part of the InnOBreed project as a case study, joining a network of European colleagues working in the same field.

Finding varieties adapted to organic fruit growing and to limited growing conditions, sanitary and pedo-climatic, showing robustness and low “susceptibility” to climatic risks is of major interest for CTIFL. Methods developed in the frame of the InnOBreed project can contribute to this objective at a European scale in order to take into account the diversity of environment. For example, the use of a model to forecast variety budburst and flowering time can contribute to a better understanding of adaptation of cultivars to their environment without planting trees in many sites. Also, non-destructive tools for fruit quality and maturity assessment adapted to a great number of varieties and species could be used.

InnOBreed also provides the possibility to discover new genotypes of interest for organic growing to assess in our plots.

In addition, CTIFL activities can contribute to the InnOBreed project by testing technical or non-sociological varietal innovations in our trials, on multiple agronomic as well as qualitative criteria. The varietal innovation are characterized from the orchard through storage and tasting including some criteria more specific to organic farming: yield regularity, susceptibility to pests and diseases. CTIFL is unique in that its governance brings together all operators in the sector, from production to retail. Events and training courses are organised to transfer information on varieties to these operators.

You can find more information about CTIFL on the website:
www.ctifl.fr
Or by contacting Sandrine Codarin:
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More information can be accessed through the links below:

- **Apricot varieties sheets for organic farming**
- **Apricot maturity chart for organic farming**
- **Organic Apricot varieties comparator**

